

Nitrogen Mustards. Part II

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Some mono- and di-(β -hydroxyethyl)amino-pyrimidine and - phthalazine and their corresponding mono-chloro compounds have been prepared.

A halogen atom at 2-position in pyrimidine and at 1-position in phthalazine is known to be reactive. Ethanolamine and diethanolamine are therefore expected to react with 2-chloropyrimidine and 1-chlorophthalazine with the elimination of hydrogen chloride to provide compounds of types (I), (II), (IV), and (V). This reaction has now been investigated and compounds (I), (II), and (IV) have been prepared. Compounds (II) and (IV) have been converted to the corresponding chloro derivatives (III and VI).

I: R= NH. CH₂.CH₂OH.

II: R= N(CH₂.CH₂OH)₂.

III: R= NH.CH₂.CH₂Cl.

IV: R= NH.CH₂.CH₂OH.

V: R= N(CH₂.CH₂OH)₂.

VI: R= NH.CH₂.CH₂Cl.

In the condensation of 2-chloropyrimidine with ethanolamine to obtain compound(I), an excess of ethanolamine was used for the purpose of removing the hydrogen chloride liberated. After refluxing, the reaction mixture showed a positive test with silver nitrate, indicating condensation. From the reaction mixture, a white crystalline compound, m.p. 77-78°, was obtained in rather a low yield. This substance could have structure (I) only. On the basis of mixed m.p. determination, compound (I) was found to be identical with the product previously obtained by us from the reaction of ethylene oxide and 2-aminopyrimidine¹.

Diethanolamine failed to condense with 2-chloropyrimidine to provide (II) under the above conditions. As such, the condensation was carried out in presence of sodium acetate (for binding the acid liberated) in *n*-propanol as a solvent. The reaction mixture, after refluxing, responded positive to the test for chloride ions.

The reaction between 1-chloro-4-methylphthalazine and ethanolamine was also smooth in *n*-butanol. The yield of product(IV) was quite high(82%). The reaction between

diethanolamine and 1-chloro-4-methylphthalazine did not, however, yield the expected product (V).

The chloro derivatives (III) and (VI) were prepared from the corresponding bases (I) and (IV) by reaction with thionyl chloride in a suitable solvent. In both cases the product was isolated quite easily. Surprisingly, the compounds did not form quarternary salts or polymerise².

Kogon *et al.*³ prepared 2-chloropyrimidino, but we obtained it in poorer yield. In attempting to improve the yield, working at a much lower temperature was found to provide a better (30%) yield.

*EXPERIMENTAL

2-Chloropyrimidine was prepared by the method of Kogon *et al.*³ with the following modifications: The temperatures, wherever mentioned, were maintained at some 5° to 10° below that recommended by the authors.³ Thus 30% yield was obtained. The product was crystallised from hexane, instead of from isopentane, in white silky needles (17.5g., 30% from 49 g. of 2-aminopyrimidine), m.p. 65-66°. (Found: N, 24.81. Calc. for C₄H₅N₂Cl: N, 24.45%).

2-(β-Hydroxyethyl) aminopyrimidine(I).—2-Chloropyrimidino (0.05*M*, 5.8 g.) was added to freshly distilled othanolamine (0.15*M*, 9.5 g.) in a flask, fitted with a reflux condenser and CaCl₂ guard tube. It was cooled and then heated for 24 hr. at 110°. Sodium carbonate (3.5 g., anhydrous) and benzene (50 ml) were then added and the mixture was refluxed for 20 min. on a water bath, cooled, and filtered. The filtrate was concentrated to a small volume (20 ml) and left overnight in a refrigerator when needle-shaped crystals separated. These were recrystallised from benzene (charcoal) in white needles (24%, 1.68 g.), m.p. 77-78°. (Found: N, 30.55. C₅H₉ON₂ requires N, 30.21%). On admixture with the product¹ from ethylene oxide and 2-aminopyrimidine, there was no depression in m.p.

2-[Di-(β-hydroxyethyl)]aminopyrimidine (II).—To a solution of 2-chloropyrimidine (0.03*M*, 3.44 g.) in *n*-propanol (50 ml) diethanolamine (0.03*M*, 3.15 g.) and fused sodium acetate (3 g.) were added and the mixture was refluxed for 24 hr. on a water bath (guard tube, NaOH pellets). The solution was kept overnight in a refrigerator and then filtered. After removing the solvent under reduced pressure, the residue was mixed with anhydrous sodium carbonate (3 g.) and dry chloroform (50 ml) with thorough shaking and kept in a refrigerator (to help crystallise the sodium acetate and sodium chloride) for 14 hr. and then filtered. Chloroform was removed under reduced pressure from the filtrate with warming and the brown thick liquid heated over a hot plate (80-90°) with constant shaking under reduced pressure (water pump) for a few minutes when the unchanged 2-chloropyrimidine sublimed. The brown semisolid residue was left overnight at the room temperature (32°) when the whole mass solidified. It was recrystallised from xylene (charcoal) in white needles (55%,

*All melting points are uncorrected.

2. Dr. R. Schmalz (private communication) states that the side chain is knocked off due to the oxidising action of SOCl₂ and sulphur separates.

3. "Organic Syntheses", 1955, Vol. 35, p. 4, John Wiley & Sons, Inc., New York.

3 g.), m.p. 72-73°. (Found: N, 22.40. $C_9H_{12}O_2N_2$ requires N, 22.95%). *Picrate*, m.p. 114-15° (bancano). (Found: N, 20.86. $C_{14}H_{16}O_7N_6$ requires N, 20.39%).

1-(β -Hydroxyethyl) amino-4-methylphthalazine (IV).—A mixture of 1-chloro-4-methylphthalazine^{4,5} (0.008M, 1.5 g.), freshly distilled ethanolamine (0.03M, 1.8 g.) and *n*-butanol (50 ml) was refluxed (CaCl₂ guard tube) for 36 hr. on a water bath. On cooling, anhydrous sodium carbonate (5 g.) was added to the mixture and it was kept in a refrigerator for 5 days. *n*-Butanol (50 ml) was again added and the mixture refluxed for 30 min. on a water bath. It was filtered hot and the filtrate concentrated (25 ml). On cooling, crystals separated. The mother liquor deposited another crop of crystals on cooling in ice. The product was recrystallised from *n*-butanol (charcoal) in white needles (82%, 1.4 g.), m.p. 195-96°. (Found: N, 21.36. $C_{11}H_{13}ON_2$ requires N, 20.70%). *Picrate*, m.p. 158-60° (ethanol). (Found: N, 20.21. $C_{17}H_{16}O_8N_6$ requires N, 19.44%).

2-(β -Chloroethyl) aminopyrimidine (III).—The amine derivative (I) (0.3M, 4.17 g.) was dissolved in a mixture of dry chloroform (10 ml) and chlorobenzene (5 ml). The solution was warmed to 50° and thionyl chloride (0.03M, 4 g.) in chlorobenzene (5 ml) was added dropwise with stirring during 15 min. (moisture was excluded during the whole process) and it was then refluxed on a water bath for 1 hr. Ice-cold water (20 ml) was then added to the hot reaction mixture which was left to cool in ice. The aqueous layer was separated, treated with a small excess of 40% NaOH solution, and extracted with chloroform (50 ml). The chloroform layer was washed with a little water and dried for 24 hr. over Na₂SO₄. The solvent was evaporated under reduced pressure at the room temperature (30°) when a yellow solid (52%, 2.5 g.) was obtained. It was crystallised in yellowish rods from ethanol (charcoal), m.p. 274-75° (decomp.). (Found: N, 27.02. $C_8H_8N_2Cl$ requires N, 26.67%).

1-(β -Chloroethyl) amino-4-methylphthalazine (VI).—Thionyl chloride (0.5 g.), dissolved in dry chloroform (10 ml), was added dropwise at 30° to a suspension of (IV) (0.4 g.) in dry chloroform (25 ml). The mixture was then refluxed on a water bath for 1 hr. (CaCl₂ guard tube). Ice-cold water was then added to the mixture and the organic layer separated and dried (Na₂SO₄). The solvents were evaporated in vacuum at the room temperature, leaving behind a brown mass. This was recrystallised from *n*-butanol (charcoal) as cream-coloured microcrystals (27.5%, 0.12 g.), m.p. 300°. (Found: N, 18.48. $C_{11}H_{12}N_2Cl$ requires N, 18.96%).

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4. Yale, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1947, 69, 1547.

5. Gabriel *et al.*, *Ber.*, 1893, 26, 705.